

Mechanical coupling between metal liner and composite structure in type III tanks during high pressure fatigue loading.

*D. Perreux^{1,4}, L. Farines¹, F. Thiebaud^{1,4}, D. Chapelle^{1,4}, P. Robinet¹, M. Weber², H. Barthélémy³, F.Barbier²
¹ MAHYTEC, Dole - France, ² Air Liquide Research Center Paris-Saclay, Jouy-en-Josas – France,
³ Air Liquide, Paris – France, ⁴ UFC-Besançon-France
 * Corresponding author (dominique.perreux@mahytec.com)

Keywords: *Composite tank, high pressure, fatigue, coupling, liner*

1 Abstract

In this paper we present an original analysis of the life prediction in fatigue loading of type III tanks. This type of tank is made of a metallic liner (steel or aluminum) and a composite structure for load bearing. The fatigue failure of a type III tank is due to the leakage of the liner (leak before burst-failure).

By using an experimental analysis we have observed that the fatigue failure of a tank type III is governed by two phenomena :

- a material rupture : due to the accumulation of damage in the liner inducing leakage. The biaxial tensile stresses in the liner are the main cause of this damage
- a structural rupture: due to local buckling of the liner induced by external pressure applied by the composite structure when the tank is discharged. This buckling induces leakage.

Depending on the target of the working pressure of the tank, it seems logical for the designer to reinforce the composite structure in order to avoid the first type of failure.

But this improvement of the composite structure has a negative effect on the liner by favoring the second phenomenon.

For a given liner, we can symbolize this principle in the following diagram

Figure 1 : Schematic failure process of type III tanks

For a liner and for low fatigue pressure the composite is adapted and the first failure phenomenon is observed. The corresponding number of cycles to failure is normally specified by the design standard. To address high service pressure, the composite structure is adapted and improved (increase of the thickness for instance). However, if the pressure cycle is too high, i.e. above the transition pressure leading to a structural failure, this leads to a drastic reduction of life. This transition pressure

depends on the composite structure and on the liner (geometry and mechanical properties).

The transition to structural failure thus limits the working pressure of a tank. In this paper we will describe this analysis and the numerical simulation providing the transition pressure.

2. General Introduction

Research for alternative sources of energy for fossil fuels unquestionably is an economical and environmental challenge. It is obvious that within this context, hydrogen is particularly interesting. It is the most promising energy carrier regarding its calorific power, non-polluting use and capacity to generate power when used with a fuel cell [1-5].

Fig 2 : Relative comparison of Lower Heating Value per mass of various fuels

Nevertheless, in order to respond to the economic and environmental criteria, hydrogen production and storage have to be improved.

Hydrogen can be stored as a compressed gas, in a liquid form or in metal hydrides. The first type of storage can be realized in four kinds of pressure vessels: (a) Type 1 refers to an all

metal cylinder, (b) Type 2 is a load-bearing metal liner hoop wrapped with resin-impregnated continuous fibre, (c) Type 3 is a load-bearing metal liner - which prevents gas diffusion & bear more than 10% of the load - wrapped with resin-impregnated continuous filament which is used as a mechanical strengthening piece, and (d) Type 4 refers to a non-load-bearing, most often non-metal liner wrapped with resin-impregnated continuous filament.

Fig 3: Various types of high pressure hydrogen tank

For Hydrogen Energy applications, the fibre is generally a carbon fibre. This work focuses on gaseous storage under high pressure using a type III vessel. This type of storage offers a lot of advantage such as no permeation risk or lightness.

The main problem encountered with this type of vessels is related to fatigue life. Most of type III tanks are designed with a 350 bar working pressure. For such pressure this offers a lot of advantage in agreement with the standard [6,7], requiring 12000 cycles at hydraulic test pressure. For higher pressure, typically 700 bar, the fatigue performance when it is subjected to

cyclic pressure loading is not in agreement with the same standard.

Taking into account that the main load bearing structure in this tank is the composite one, the first idea about this problem could be to increase the thickness of composite in order to increase the service pressure, but this simple idea is not realistic [8], because the phenomena under fatigue for this type of tank is more complex and is a mixture of several phenomena which compete to the failure.

Figure 3: Section of a type III vessel

3. Stress assessment in the type III Tank from manufacturing to loading.

To analyse the failure in fatigue of type III tank it is useful to consider first what happens in a simple long composite hybrid tube made of a metallic liner and composite structure. This example allows to consider the various phenomena.

Let us consider a metallic tube (steel or aluminium). The external diameter is R and e_L is the thickness. Around this tube a composite structure is wrapped (for instance carbon T700/Epoxy matrix), the stacking sequence is $[+/-\theta_p, 90_n]_m$, where (n,p,m) are the number of layer. This type of composite structure is just an example close to the one of Tank Type III. The composite structure has a thickness noted e_c

After the filament winding process the structure can be considered as compact.

Figure 4 :Hybrid Metal/Composite tubes before curing

The second stage of the manufacturing is the curing. During the curing stage depending of the composite structure, a gap can appear between liner and composite structure due to the difference between thermal expansion coefficient of composite structure and metal liner.

Figure 5: Hybrid Metal/Composite tubes after curing

It is obvious that this gap is depending of the composite structure and at the opposite a "radial compression" of the liner can be observed by the composite structure.

With real Type III tank this gap is often observed due to the composite structure which must be dimensioning with respect to the pressure loading. This pressure loading induces that the hoop stress is the highest one and then in the composite stacking sequence the 90° layer is the most present. These 90 layers due to their orientation are mainly responsible for the gap.

The figure 5 shows the initial structure. From this point, the pressure loading can be performed.

To simplify the analysis it is considered that the thin wall theory can be applied here for instance by assuming $R > 0.1(e_L + e_C)$. Considering the material strain-stress relation for the composite and for the metal liner. We reduce the analysis to the plane stress. z and θ are respectively the axe of the cylinder direction and the hoop direction.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_z^L \\ \sigma_\theta^L \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{zz}^L & S_{z\theta}^L \\ S_{z\theta}^L & S_{\theta\theta}^L \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_z^L \\ \varepsilon_\theta^L \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_z^C \\ \sigma_\theta^C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{zz}^C & S_{z\theta}^C \\ S_{z\theta}^C & S_{\theta\theta}^C \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_z^C \\ \varepsilon_\theta^C \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Due to the gap between the metal liner and the composite structure, when the pressure grows from zero to the maximum pressure P_{max} , all the stress is first born by the liner alone.

At any time the stress is related to the stress assessed with the thin wall theory:

$$2\sigma_z^L = \sigma_\theta^L = \frac{PR}{e_C} \quad (3)$$

where P is the internal pressure.

This situation is prolonged until the hoop strain of the liner is $\varepsilon^{contact}$

$$\varepsilon^{contact} = \frac{R + e_L + Gap}{R + e_L} \quad (4)$$

When the liner strain is $\varepsilon^{contact}$ indeed the external diameter is in contact with the internal part of the composite structure. This stain in the liner is obtained when the pressure is $P^{contact}$

$$P^{contact} = \frac{R(2S_{zz}^C - S_{z\theta}^C)}{2e_C(S_{zz}^C S_{\theta\theta}^C - S_{z\theta}^C S_{z\theta}^C)} \varepsilon^{contact} \quad (5)$$

At this point the composite structure can be considered as linked to the liner and then the strain of each material are the same (taking into account the hypothesis of the thin wall theory) and the stress are assessed by:

$$2(\sigma_z^C + \sigma_z^L) = \sigma_\theta^C + \sigma_\theta^L = \frac{PR}{(e_C + e_L)} \quad (6)$$

Then after this contact point, the strain stress relation is provided by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_z^C \\ \varepsilon_\theta^C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} e_L \begin{bmatrix} S_{zz}^L & S_{z\theta}^L \\ S_{z\theta}^L & S_{\theta\theta}^L \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \\ e_C \begin{bmatrix} S_{zz}^C & S_{z\theta}^C \\ S_{z\theta}^C & S_{\theta\theta}^C \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_z \\ \Sigma_\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

With :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_z \\ \Sigma_\theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(P - P^{Contact})R}{(e_C + e_L)} \\ \frac{(P - P^{Contact})R}{2(e_C + e_L)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

and,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_z^L - \epsilon_z^{contact} \\ \epsilon_\theta^L - \epsilon_\theta^{contact} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_z^C \\ \epsilon_\theta^C \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

These strain-strain relationship is prolonged up to the point where the liner starts to plastify. Usually the Yield point is obtained when the strain in the liner verifies the Von Mises criteria.

$$\sqrt{(\sigma_z^L)^2 + \sigma_\theta^L)^2 - \sigma_z^L \sigma_\theta^L} = Y \quad (10)$$

When the Pressure increases from $P^{contact}$ to P^{max} the yield point can be reached. The pressure where the yield point is obtained by the following equation combining equations from all the previous equations. This pressure is noted P^{Plas}

At this point the strain of the liner starts to be elastoplastic. In this case the strain stress relation is no longer linear and must be described as a elastoplastic model with isotropic or kinematics hardening [9]. This situation is prolonged upto P^{max} . At this last point the liner is plastified and the maximum plastic strains are noted :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{z,Plast}^L \\ \epsilon_{\theta,Plast}^L \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Now consider the deloading. Both materials are elastic and deloaded. In this case the strain of the liner decreased with respect to the equation 1, when for the composite the stress decrease with the relation (2).

Due to the plastic deformation for a certain pressure the state of strain of the liner will be such as to continue to decrease a global compression must be applied on the liner. For the same pressure the composite structure will be always under tension. Then the composite will start to compress the liner.

When the system will be fully deloaded by the pressure, the liner will be under compression as it could be alone under external pressure. This external pressure related to the state of stress of the composite and the expression of strain given by (11).

$$P_{External}^L = P_{External}^L(\epsilon_{z,Plast}^L, \epsilon_{\theta,Plast}^L, P^{Max}, S^C, S^L, Y, R, e_c, e_L) \quad (12)$$

The following figure draws the diagrammatical evolution of the hoop stress for the liner end for the composite structure.

Figure 6: Hoop Stress (Blue -Liner, Red-Composite) versus Pressure

This apparent external pressure can lead to buckling of the liner. For instance it is well known that for long tube the Euler analysis provides buckling pressure related to the liner dimension and the elastic properties.

$$P_{External}^L = \left(\frac{E}{R}\right)^3 \frac{E}{4(1-\nu^2)} \quad (13)$$

In reality this relation is valid for long tube without end effect. For cylindrical shell tank it is a sort of limit because tanks cannot be considered as relevant of this hypothesis.

This long analytical presentation allows to understand why it is observed located buckling in the liner when the applied pressure increase. This mode of failure is observed especially for high pressure.

On another hand to be able to load a tank at high pressure large composite reinforcement is required, depending on the stiffness of composite the maximum strain is roughly the same. But due to the volume of composite, the compliance of the composite structure increases and the apparent external pressure on the liner after deloading increases also. Then for high

pressure, the buckling is the failure for most of hybrid composite tubes.

For low pressure, less composite is used and then the global compliance of the composite structure is lower. Then the risk of buckling failure decreases. For lower pressure the main risk is due to the leakage provided by accumulation of plastic strain. This risk can be decreased by choosing adapted composite structure. The transition pressure is the one which shares the pressure between with both modes. This transition pressure is the maximum service pressure for a tank of type III.

4) Numerical and experimental analysis

The previous analytical analysis allows to understand why the fatigue of type III is a problem. But this analytical assessment does not give a precise value of this transition value, because it is difficult to take into account of the plasticity and because the equation (13) is not valid, and also because the thin wall theory is no longer valid.

Then numerical analysis has to be used for such analysis.

For example consider a tank made of steel with $R = 100\text{mm}$. These tanks have been made and tested by Mahytec Ltd.

Figure 7 : Type III tank before test

Finite element analysis allows to simulate the stress in the wall of this tank.

Figure 8 : Experimental Hoop strain on the composite surface versus pressure- The gap effect can be observed, no strain with pressure > 50 bars .

Figure 9 : Numerical simulation of the Hoop strain on the composite surface versus pressure- The gap effect is also observed. Positive strain after deloading is observed.

Taking into account this numerical analysis, the effect of transition pressure or limite pressure can be observed. One element which has been especially analysed is the role of the carbone fiber type.

We have assessed the role of different types of fibers on the transition pressure .

Figure 10: Effect of the fiber types on the limit of nominal pressure for the tank analyzed.

It has been observed for the liner analyzed with T700, maximum service pressure is around 500 bars, when it can be 800 bars when M40J is used.

5) Conclusion

In this study we have proposed a model to understand the fatigue problem observed on type III. The phenomena and the base of the model have been explained with analytical analysis.

Two types of failure are observed for high pressure: the failure (leakage) is due to local buckling, when for moderate and low pressure the failure (leakage) is due to damage of the liner due to plasticity accumulation. The transition between both phenomena is called transition pressure, and it is the limit pressure for the tank, with the type of composite structure used to make it.

In order to assess the value of the limit of the nominal pressure, numerical method is required. In this paper we have assessed as example the

effect of the carbon fiber type on the maximal nominal pressure that this tank is able to support.

section, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 31, (2006) 627 – 638

6) References :

- [1] DOE, 2012 Annual Progress Report, http://www.hydrogen.energy.gov/annual_progress12.html
- [2] John Andrews, Bahman Shabani, Re-envisioning the role of hydrogen in a sustainable energy economy *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Volume 37, Issue 2, January 2012, Pages 1184-1203
- [3] Akos Kriston, Tamás Szabó, György Inzelt, The marriage of car sharing and hydrogen economy: A possible solution to the main problems of urban living. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Volume 35, Issue 23, December 2010, Pages 12697-12708
- [4] John Andrews, Bahman Shabani, Where does Hydrogen Fit in a Sustainable Energy Economy, *Procedia Engineering*, Volume 49, 2012, Pages 15-25
- [5] Jinyang Zheng, Xianxin Liu, Ping Xu, Pengfei Liu, Yongzhi Zhao, Jian Yang, Development of high pressure gaseous hydrogen storage technologies, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Volume 37, Issue 1, January 2012, Pages 1048-1057
- [6] ISO/TS 12245, Transportable gas cylinders. Fully wrapped composite cylinders
- [7] ISO/TS 15869, Gaseous hydrogen and hydrogen blends - Land vehicle fuel tanks.
- [8] O. Comond, D. Perreux, F. Thiebaud, M. Weber, Methodology to improve the lifetime of type III HP tank with a steel liner *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Volume 34, Issue 7, April 2009, Pages 3077-3090
- [9] D. Chapelle, D. Perreux, Optimal design of type 3 Hydrogen storage vessels : Part I : Analytical modeling of the cylindrical